

PL4XGL: A Programming Language Approach to Explainable Graph Learning

Artifact Manual

This artifact aims to reproduce the main results of the technique PL4XGL in our paper “PL4XGL: A Programming Language Approach to Explainable Graph Learning” submitted to PLDI 2024. Specifically, following this artifact will reproduce the results of PL4XGL in Figure 11, Table 5 in our paper (paper.pdf), and Figure 2 of our supplementary material (supplementary_text.pdf).

1 Getting Started Guide

1.1 Requirements

- Python 3.x (we used python 3.8.8)

1.2 Verifying Installation (Basic Testing)

Move to the directory “GraphClassification”. Then, run the following command:

```
$ python3 eval.py -d MUTAG
```

The trained model is already included in the artifact in “GraphClassification/datasets/MUTAG/learned_GDL_programs/bu” folder. The above command will produce predictions and explanations for the MUTAG (test) dataset. If the artifact is successfully installed, you will see the following results:

```
-----  
Test graphs : 20  
Correctly classified graphs : 20  
Test Accuracy : 1.0  
-----  
Elapsed time: 0:00:05.656562
```

The above results illustrate that the model classified 20 test graphs and correctly classified all of them; the accuracy of the model is 1.0 (Table 5 of our paper). The classification took 5.6 seconds. Note that the above instruction may report the different classification times due to the differences in the experiment environments. In our paper, all the experiments on PL4XGL are conducted on a machine with AMD Ryzen Threadripper 3990X with 64 cores.

2 Step-by-Step Instructions

The following instructions will reproduce the results of PL4XGL for the eleven datasets in our paper and supplementary material.

2.1 Reproducing PL4XGL for the Three Graph Classification Datasets

Following the instructions below reproduces the results of PL4XGL for the three graph classification datasets MUTAG, BBBP, and BACE in Table 5 and Figure 11 of our paper and Figure 2 of our supplementary material. First, move to the directory “GraphClassification”.

Reproducing accuracy. The command for evaluating the accuracy of the trained model for a dataset is as follows:

```
$ python3 eval.py -d <dataset>
```

where `dataset` can be one of the following datasets:

```
MUTAG, BBBP, BACE
```

Then, the command will reproduce the accuracy of PL4XGL for the dataset in Table 5.

Reproducing explainability. For reproducing *Fidelity*, *Sparsity*, *Generality*, and *Precision*, run the following command:

```
$ python3 explainability.py -d <dataset>
```

Then, the command will reproduce the results of *Fidelity*, *Sparsity*, *Generality*, and *Precision* for the dataset in Figure 11 of our paper and Figure 2 of our supplementary material. In MUTAG dataset (i.e., if you type `$ python3 explainability.py MUTAG`), for example, the command will produce the following results:

```
...
Average
Sparsity : 0.5098225502331035
Fidelity : 0.0
Generality : 0.485299059139785
Precision : 1.0
```

The above results illustrate that the *Sparsity*, *Fidelity*, *Generality*, and *Precision* of the model are 0.5098, 0.0, 0.4853, and 1.0, respectively.

Learning a new model. To learn a new model for a dataset, run the following command:

```
$ python3 learn.py -d <dataset> -c <numcores>
```

where `<numcores>` is the number of cores (default = 1) to use for learning the model. Note that the above command will remove the pre-trained model in the artifact and learn a new model for the dataset. The learned model will be stored in the “NodeClassification/datasets/<dataset>/learned_GDL_programs/td” folder. For example, if you type `$ python3 learn.py -d MUTAG -c 64`, the command will learn a new model for the MUTAG dataset using 4 cores. If the learning is successful, the command will produce the following results:

```
...
=====
#Used cores : 64
Total training time: 0:04:06.370243
=====
```

The above results illustrate that the learning used 4 cores and took about 4 minutes.

2.2 Reproducing PL4XGL for the Eight Node Classification Datasets

Following the instructions below reproduces the results of PL4XGL for the eight node classification datasets BA-SHAPES, TREE-CYCLES, TEXAS, WISCONSIN, CORNELL, CORA, CITESEER, and PUBMEDBACE in Table 5 and Figure 11 of our paper and Figure 2 of our supplementary material. First, move to the directory “NodeClassification”.

Reproducing accuracy. The command for evaluating the accuracy of the trained model for a dataset is as follows:

```
$ python3 eval.py -d <dataset>
```

where `dataset` can be one of the following datasets:

BA-Shapes, Tree-Cycles, Wisconsin, Texas, Cornell, Cora, Citeseer, Pubmed

Then, the command will reproduce the accuracy of PL4XGL for the dataset in Table 5.

Reproducing explainability. For reproducing *Fidelity*, *Sparsity*, *Generality*, and *Precision*, run the following command:

```
$ python3 explainability.py -d <dataset>
```

Then, the command will reproduce the results of *Fidelity*, *Sparsity*, *Generality*, and *Precision* for the dataset in Figure 11 of our paper and Figure 2 of our supplementary material. In TEXAS dataset (i.e., if you type `$ python3 explainability.py Texas`), for example, the command will produce the following results:

```
...
Average
Fidelity : 0.0
Sparsity : 0.9020536916747732
Generality : 0.46196750780084117
Precision : 0.9564478829925053
```

The above results illustrate that the *Sparsity*, *Fidelity*, *Generality*, and *Precision* of the model are 0.9021, 0.0, 0.4620, and 0.9564, respectively.

Learning a new model. To learn a new model for a dataset, run the following command:

```
$ python3 learn.py -d <dataset> -c <numcores>
```

where `<numcores>` is the number of cores (default = 1) to use for learning the model. The above command will remove the pre-trained model in the artifact and learn a new model for the dataset. For example, if you type `$ python3 learn.py -d BA-Shapes -c 4`, the command will learn a new model for the TEXAS dataset using 4 cores. If the learning is successful, the command will produce the following results:

```
...
=====
#Used cores : 4
Total training time: 0:00:08.639183
=====
```

The above results illustrate that the learning used 4 cores and took 8.6 seconds. The learned model will be stored in the “NodeClassification/datasets/<dataset>/learned_GDL_programs/td” folder.